

Nature-based playgrounds in Barcelona:
Evaluating the impact of naturalising schoolyards
through the Transformem els Patis project.

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Contents

Contents	2
1. Introduction	4
2. Theoretical framework.....	6
2.1 The benefits of nature on health, well-being, and development	6
2.2 Naturalizing Schoolyards	7
2.3 Naturalizing Pedagogy	8
3. Case Studies	12
3.1 Selected schools	12
3.2 About the Transformem els Patis initiative	12
3.3 Social context and schoolyard description.....	14
3.3.1 School A - La Dreta de l'Eixample	15
3.3.2 School B – Vallbona	18
3.3.3 School C - El Poblenou	21
3.3.4 School D - La Font d'en Fargues	23
4. Methods.....	25
4.1 Physical Patio Evaluation.....	25
4.2 Social behaviour and play observation.....	26
4.3 Interviews.....	31
5. Results.....	33
5.1 Naturalised Patio Evaluation.....	34
5.1.1 Category 1- Green and Brown	35
5.1.2 Category 2- Design and Maintenance	35
5.1.3 Category 3 - Play, learning and socialising	36

5.1.4 Category 4 - Water	37
5.1.5 Category 5 - Habitat for animals.....	37
5.1.6 Key findings	37
5.2 Observation of social and play behaviour.....	38
5.2.1 School A - Transformed	38
5.2.2 School B – Transformed.....	40
5.2.3 School C – Untransformed.....	42
5.2.4 School D – Untransformed.....	44
5.2.5 Key findings	45
5.3 Interviews.....	46
5.3.1 Naturalised schools (A and B)	47
5.3.2 Un-naturalised schools (C and D)	50
5.3.3 Key findings	52
6.Discussion	54
7.Bibliography	59
Appendix.....	62
A. Visualisations of observed behaviour	62
B. Visualisations of observed physical play	64
C. Visualisations of observed creative play.....	66
D. Naturalised Patio Evaluation Tool	68
E. Use of patio- observation recording sheet	70
F. Interview question sheet	71

1. Introduction

Schoolyards of Barcelona city's school, like many cities across Spain, are most often characterised as empty concrete spaces, that favour the playing of sports and little, if not nothing else (Lucas & Dymont, 2010). This type of playground design offers two spaces for students to occupy during breaktime: to be involved in playing competitive ball sports, often dominated by boys, or standing around the edge, often dominated by girls, creating strong division in the student body and giving them little opportunity to interact (Snow et al., 2019). The atmosphere this creates is one of high energy, high stress and competitiveness, often leading to conflict. Furthermore, in the Mediterranean climate of Barcelona, these exposed concrete areas create urban heat islands, raising the temperature even high and providing little protection from the heat and the sun (Serrano-Jiménez et al., 2021).

Due to climate concerns and a growing awareness and understanding of the social, cognitive and emotional benefits that a more diverse and natural schoolyard can offer students, there is an increasing desire from many schools, to transform their schoolyards, and funding from government and non-government sources, are helping schools realise these transformations. This project focuses on four schools, in different districts of Barcelona City, that have taken part in the project Transformem els Patis promoted by the Ajuntament of Barcelona through the Directorate of Education, with the collaboration of the Barcelona Institute for Children and Adolescents and the Associació de Mestres Rosa Sensat. This program aims to improve the recreational and play space so that they are more naturalised, promote equality between students based on the diversification of play, and to promote community uses as a neighbourhood facility. Two of the schools studied will be undergoing works on their schoolyard in the summer of 2025 and two were transformed in the summer of 2023. For each of the schools I (1) assess how natural the space is, using a patio evaluation tool, (2) observe how students use the space, and (3) interview two educators (per school), asking for their perceptions of the transformation process, their reasons for

taking part in the process, how the schoolyard space is used by students, and if relevant, what changes in students have been perceived since the transformation.

Through this mixed methods approach, I find that naturalised schoolyards lead to a richer diversity and greater equity of play and social interaction between students, less conflict and offer a greater opportunity for outdoor learning. Secondly, I find that while there is a strong desire for transformation to provide diverse option of play, there is a resistance to greening in the naturalisation process. Finally, I find that the impact of the transformation and use of the space, both pre and post transformation, is strongly influenced by and dependent on the mindset and culture of each school community.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 The benefits of nature on health, well-being, and development

The numerous benefits of interaction with nature has long been documented. Kaplan and Kaplan's book, *The Experience of Nature: A Psychological Perspective* published in 1989, discusses the numerous benefits of exposure to nature such as improving focus, problem-solving, and mental clarity; reduces mental fatigue and stress; promoting relaxation, mood enhancement, and creativity; improving concentration, problem-solving skills, and memory, which in turn can support learning and academic performance. Today, there are a wealth of theories and studies that discuss the benefits of nature on mental and physical well-being (Jimenez et al., 2021; Nejade et al., 2022) and a growing body of research highlighting the importance of interaction with nature for children specifically (Ly & Vella-Brodrick, 2024; van Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2018; Vella-Brodrick & Gilowska, 2022).

Stress Recovery Theory suggests that exposure to natural environments facilitates psychological and physiological recovery from stress by reducing blood pressure, heart rate, and cortisol levels (Ulrich et al., 1991). Exposure to greenery and natural environments has been linked to lower stress levels, improved mood and increased resilience which supports emotional well-being and mental health (Chawla et al., 2014). Attention Restoration Theory, suggests that natural settings help replenish cognitive resources depleted by sustained attention, thereby improving focus, memory, and academic performance (Kaplan, 1995). Outdoor learning and regular exposure to nature, for example, in green playgrounds, have been shown to enhance attention, memory, and overall cognitive functioning, though further studies are needed to strengthen findings and observe and analyse long term impacts on children's cognitive development (Vella-Brodrick & Gilowska, 2022). It is also suggested that natural

environments can promote more positive social interactions between children (Ly & Vella-Brodrick, 2024; van Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2018).

Naturalized schoolyards can offer more equitable use of the space between different students, in comparison to concrete or sports-pitch based schoolyards. They can provide more opportunities for play between different ages and genders by providing a diversity of play options outside of traditional competitive ball sports (Lucas & Dymont, 2010). Natural environments provide diverse opportunities for physical activity, the development of motor skills as well as creativity. Further to this, due to its unpredictability and ever-changing nature, exploration and unstructured play in natural environments can help foster problem-solving, ingenuity and flexible thinking (Kiewra & Veselack, 2016; Moore, 2014). Natural objects such as sticks, logs and leaves, can transform from one thing into another, encouraging imagination and creativity and removing boundaries of 'correct' actions or types of play. Loose Parts Theory, coined by Nicholson in 1971, suggests the importance not only of natural materials, but also of materials or objects with not set function, that can be picked up, moved and manipulated. As well as fostering curiosity and connection to nature, this type of open-ended play provides space for communication between children to decide how the imaginative play will evolve, which can in turn help the development of decision making skills, creativity, and imagination and problem solving skills as well as building confidence (A Spencer et al., 2019; Gull et al., 2019; Moore, 2014).

2.2 Naturalizing Schoolyards

Despite the numerous reported benefits, many children lack regular exposure to nature, especially those living in urban settings. Furthermore, many schoolyards, particularly those in cities, offer little to no natural play opportunities. Instead, favouring concrete surfaces and little other options other than competitive ball games (Lucas & Dymont, 2010). Naturalising schoolyards can provide an opportunity for children, particularly those living in cities without easy access to nature, to experience the benefits of exposure to, and play in, natural environments in their day to day.

As awareness of the many benefits of naturalised and diverse schoolyards increases, initiatives that encourage and facilitate schoolyard greening are also increasing. Some of the government-led programs in European cities include “Transformem els patis” and “Refugis Climatics” in Barcelona, “Oasis” in Paris, “Opération Ré-création” in Brussels, “Groenblauwe Schoolpleinen” in Rotterdam and “Amsterdamse Impuls schoolpleinen” in Amsterdam (Sekulova & Mallén, 2024). And as transformations to schoolyards are being made, it presents an opportunity to study and analyse the impact of these on students, school culture and attitudes and pedagogy. More research is needed showing the impact of schoolyard transformations, as well as exploring the factors that allow or impede the realisation of the potential benefits the space. These factors may be related to the quality of physical transformation itself e.g. the quantity and diversity of plants and natural materials added; the amount of concrete or non-natural materials removed. However, a physical transformation alone will not necessarily lead to a total transformation in the use of the space by adults and students. For a total transformation in the understanding of how the schoolyard can be utilised and the range of benefits it can offer, it will also require a shift in conceptions and attitudes towards the benefits of play and learning in natural settings and an openness to question and transform ingrained ideas of traditional education and pedagogical methods.

2.3 Naturalizing Pedagogy

Traditional western education systems are very often entirely disconnected from nature. Nature is thought of in a tokenistic way, incorporating exposure or interaction with nature very little, if at all. Whilst the mental health benefits of connecting with nature is more widely understood and accepted, the use of nature as a co-educator, rather than something that existing outside of the main pedagogical framework, is not yet something we see in traditional public education systems and public-sector guided curriculums.

There are however, an increasing number of educational systems such as Montessori, Waldorf and Forest Schools, that are based in outdoor learning and whose pedagogies

are centered around theories such as Loose Parts Theory and integrate nature as a central pillar in education and learning; in addition to the many educators making their own efforts, whilst working within traditional learning systems. Integrating nature in this way involves learning thorough self-directed, hands-on experience in nature and supports environmental literacy and connection with nature as a result (Kiewra & Veselack, 2016; Moore, 2014).

Nature as a co-educator

Jickling, Blenkinsop and Morse, introduce the idea of Wild Pedagogies (Jickling et al., 2024). Wild Pedagogies proposes a way of teaching that breaks through the rigid boundaries of ‘normal’ western teaching practices. It is a pedagogy unlimited by cultural norms, prescriptive results-based learning, and set objectives and expectations. In it, nature becomes a co-educator; experiential learning opportunities arise and are embraced, cultivating a deep curiosity and connection to the natural world.

They offer three ‘touchstones’ that act as key principles to understand how to embody Wild Pedagogies. Touchstone 1, Nature as a Co-educator, describes involving the natural world as a part of the educational process, actively listening to and engaging with it. They ask:

‘How might more-than-human and/or material others be understood as active collaborators or instigators in pedagogical activities, rather than objects of study? In other words, how might we move on from learning about the more-than-human world to learning with and from it?’ (Jickling et al., 2024)

Working with Nature as a Co-educator reimagines our relationship with the more-than-human world, decenters the learning process and challenges the idea that humans are the sole possessors and conveyors of knowledge.

Touchstone 2 is ‘Complexity, the Unknown and Spontaneity’. This touchstone encourages educators to be open to embracing spontaneity and to take advantage of the unexpected moments that learning with and from nature can offer. For example, if a

child notices lichen growing on a tree, it may inspire questions and curiosity around what it is, why it grows, noticing if there are different types on different trees, and so on.

Touchstone 3, 'Locating the Wild', talks about finding the wild in whichever environment you find yourself in. You do not need to be in the middle of a forest to embody the values and principles of Wild Pedagogies. It is a shift in mentality on how we educate and learn, inviting the unknown and learning from our surroundings. Nature can be found anywhere, even in urban settings. A point which is particularly relevant in the context of transforming and utilising urban schoolyards.

Loose Parts Theory

In their paper exploring the perceptions of the benefits and challenges of Loose Parts Play in outdoor learning environments, Spencer et al. report educator's comments that allowing the children to engage in loose parts play in natural environments challenged their own perceptions of risk and danger, leading to a shift in their own mentality.

Educator's report many noted benefits in Loose Parts Play such as children becoming less fearful of active outdoor play and learning to take healthy risks; the development of creativity and imagination, determination and resilience; cultivating independence, confidence and leadership, as well as the building relationships between themselves.

The challenges reported include concerns over the sustainability and storage of loose parts and questions on if the success of Loose Parts Play being due to its novelty. Most interestingly, educators report an apprehension (or potential apprehension) among students, educators and parents alike, in how to use natural loose parts in play (A Spencer et al., 2019). This highlights how the introduction (or return to) unguided play, play in nature and Loose Parts Play, requires a deconstruction of ingrained ideas and learned fears around this type of play and its educational, cognitive, social and physical benefits. Furthermore, it suggests that for nature-based learning and play to become truly embedded and the space used in the most meaningful way, it may require a Whole School Approach. This would involve a total transformation of school ethos and culture, curriculum and pedagogy, professional development of staff, as well as institutional policies, to create lasting and effective change (Wals & Mathie, 2023).

Naturalising schoolyards could provide the opportunity to offer children daily access to nature, as well as the many benefits of diverse, creative and unstructured play in natural environments, who may not otherwise have it. It could also offer a space in which western educational systems and pedagogy can begin to be transformed, offering opportunities to reshape our relationship with the natural world and how we can learn from it. For this to become more present, more studies are needed to help better understand the benefits of green schoolyards, and what makes them most successful and most deeply transformative. With the growing interest in naturalising education and educational spaces, there are an increasing number of projects funding schoolyard transformation. This offers an opportunity to record and assess the impact and use of these newly naturalised spaces and offer an insight into the benefits and challenges they present.

3. Case Studies

3.1 Selected schools

For this study, four schools were selected by the Municipality of Barcelona and requested to participate. Each school is located in a different district of Barcelona Metropolitan Area: La Dreta de l'Eixample, Vallbona, El Poblenou and La Font d'en Fargues. For anonymity purposes, schools will not be referred to by name. Rather, each have been assigned a letter, and will be referred to either by their assigned letter, or by the district they are located in. All schools selected have participated in the program Transformem els Patis, organised, run and funded by the Municipality of Barcelona. Two of the selected schools took part in the 2022-2023 cycle, meaning that their schoolyards were transformed in the summer of 2023, and two of the schools are taking part in the 2024-2025 cycle, meaning that at the time of study, these schools were in the design phase of the program. The table below summarises the four schools and their location geographically, and within the program (fig. 1).

School	District	Year of participation	Current status of schoolyard
A	La Dreta de l'Eixample	2022-2023	Transformed
B	Vallbona	2022-2023	Transformed
C	El Poblenou	2024-2025	Awaiting transformation
D	La Font d'en Fargues	2024-2025	Awaiting transformation

Figure 1. Table showing the location of each school, as labelled by letter, the year they participated in the program and the status of their schoolyard regarding transformation.

3.2 About the Transformem els Patis initiative

'Transformem els Patis' translates as 'Let's transform the playgrounds' and is a program initiated and funded by the municipality of Barcelona that aims to redesign school schoolyards to be more inclusive, green, and community-oriented (Carranza et al., 2021). The schoolyard designs are based on 6 criteria:

- 1) Valuable space for learning, co-education and coexistence within the school (including gender equity, positive conflict management and inclusion of all children in shared play)

- 2) Diversity of environments and recreational and creative activities (including environments for active, semi-active and calm play, stimulating spaces and materials that allow for diverse autonomous play without instruction)
- 3) Contact with nature: greenery, land and water (including addition of vegetation and trees, creating an outdoor climate shelter, combining soft permeable ground with sand and paving, providing play elements made of natural materials and providing water for play, experiment and refreshment)
- 4) Comfort of the environment (including places of shade in the summer and sun in the winter, places to sit and find drinking water)
- 5) Balanced (re)distribution of spaces (providing quality space for a variety of games and activities, improved accessibility and combining fixed and mobile recreational items)
- 6) Diverse uses for the community and the neighbourhood (including extra-curricular activities, parties, and availability of the schoolyard to the wider neighbourhood in afternoons and at weekends)

Following the transformation of 11 schools in 2019-2020, as part of the creation of climate refuges in Barcelona city, the Transformem program was initiated in the 2020-2021 academic year. Now in its 5th year of transformations, as of 2023 a total of 71 schools had participated in the program (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2023). As part of the program, schools are guided and supported through several participative processes throughout the year, to design their new schoolyard. These meetings are made up of representatives of all parts of the school community (teachers, families, students), as well as external participants from the municipality of Barcelona and the architects who will create the design. Despite, the strong interest from schools in the program, for the current academic year 2024-2025, only 3 schools have been able to participate.

The ultimate goal of the program is that by 2030, all playgrounds in infant education, primary schools, institute schools, and special education centers in Barcelona will achieve the following objectives:

- 1) Recognise playgrounds as play spaces for excellence
- 2) Improve the naturalisation of playgrounds to guarantee spaces for the promotion of health and well-being
- 3) Promote co-education in the playgrounds to establish dynamics and equitable relationships between children and the educational community
- 4) Encourage the opening of the playgrounds to the community to create links with society and the environment.

A recent pilot evaluation of the program, comparing the physicality and use of transformed and untransformed schoolyards, found that transformed schoolyards had more natural elements, play structures and places to sit, and less cemented flooring. It also found that a higher proportion of active play and non-sport games among boys and girls was recorded in transformed school compared to untransformed schools. Finally, it noted that in transformed schoolyards, there was a lower proportion of girls who only watched and did not engage in play (Periañez et al., 2024).

3.3 Social context and schoolyard description

Using data from the Statistical Institute of Catalunya, we are able to compare the socio-economic status of the neighbourhood in which each school is situated (fig.2). It should be noted that the most recent statistic available were from 2021. In the time between 2021 to 2025 Barcelona city has suffered a rapid increase in the cost of living, namely in rent and housing prices, which may have led to changes in neighbourhood demographics across the city's districts due to financial pressures.

Several concepts. 2021: Barcelona neighbourhoods / Concept								
School	District	Employed population (%)	Low-skilled workers (%)	Population with low studies (%)	Young population without post-compulsory education (%)	Foreigners from low or middle income countries (%)	Average income per person (€)	Small Area Socioeconomic index (IST)
A	La Dreta de l'Eixample	63,3	3	6,1	6,1	10,3	21956,9	121.1
B	Vallbona	54,4	24	19,3	48,2	13,6	10132	75.5
C	El Poblenou	68,7	4,4	10,8	12,5	9,2	17671,3	95.9
D	La Font d'en Fargues	70	5,1	11,7	10,3	4,9	19606,2	118.1

Fig. 2 Table showing the values for different socio-economic indicators for 4 different districts of

Barcelona in 2021, each of which is labelled with the school that is located in that district. Source: Idescat. Small Area Socioeconomic Index.

3.3.1 School A - La Dreta de l'Eixample

La Dreta de l'Eixample has the most highly educated population of the 4 districts, with the highest average annual income per person, at €21,956.90. It has the lowest percentage of population with low studies, lowest percentage of young people without post-compulsory educational and the lowest percentage of low skilled workers. 63% of the population are employed, which lays halfway between the highest and lowest percentage of the four schools, for this concept. La Dreta de l'Eixample has the highest socio-economic status of the four districts, when comparing Small Area Socioeconomic Index, as well the selected indicators overall (fig.2).

Formed originally as an educational cooperative, this school became part of the Collective of Teachers for the Catalan Public School (CEPEPC) in 1983. It's a small school, with one class per year group, for early years and primary education (ages 3-12). The number of students currently listed by the school on their website, is 211. The school describes their student body as being mostly second generation in Catalunya, therefore Catalan not being their mother tongue spoken at home. They also report having double the number of students with additional educational and learning needs than average for schools in Catalunya. They attribute this as being due to them having an Intensive Support for Inclusive Schooling (SIEI) at the school, which has a designated teacher for the SIEI and also a special education educator (EEE) to provide attention and support to these students.

Schoolyard A - before transformation

Source: Flickr BCN. Cultura, Educació, Esports i Cicles de Vida: [Acerca de Cultura, Educació, Esports i Cicles de Vida | Flickr](#)

Schoolyard A - after transformation

Source: Authors own photos

3.3.2 School B – Vallbona

School B, located in Vallbona is the most deprived neighbourhood out of the four, with a Small Area Socioeconomic Index of 75.5. It has highest percentage population with low studies, the highest percentage of young people without post-compulsory education, the highest percentage of low skilled workers, as well as foreigners from low- and middle-income countries. It also has the lowest percentage of employment and average annual income, just €10,132 per person compared with the other 3 districts whose average annual incomes all lie between €17671.30 and €21956.90 (fig.2).

Previously classified as agricultural land, the neighbourhood of Vallbona began to form a result of migration in the 1950's. Migrants with limited financial resources built unofficial shanty houses without water, electricity or sewage services, many of which were demolished by the city council during the 1960's and 1970's. Starting in the 1990's the Catalan government has built several apartment buildings and public housing in the area, as well as making improvements to public spaces, such as pavements. The current school building was inaugurated in 1970 and was built as a result of pressure from the neighbourhood after the religious school that served the area was demolished to make way for the construction of highways which now enclose the neighbourhood. Between the demolition of the old school and the construction of the current one, classes were held in old tram wagons used as temporary classrooms.

Originally built for 800 students, the school currently reports a small cohort of 142 students, distributed as one class per year. In the coming academic year, the school will begin to provide secondary education, as the current final year primary students move into secondary education. Due to the socio-economic characteristics of Vallbona, where many families have experienced economic challenges, migration, and historical urban neglect, school B has been classified as a Center for Preferential Educational Attention. This means that it receives additional resources and support from the Catalan Department of Education, to help improve learning conditions and support students more effectively.

Schoolyard B - before transformation

Source: Flickr BCN. Cultura, Educació, Esports i Cicles de Vida: [Acerca de Cultura, Educació, Esports i Cicles de Vida | Flickr](#)

Schoolyard B - after transformation

Source: Authors own photos

3.3.3 School C - El Poblenou

As of 2021, El Poblenou was reported as having a relatively high employment percentage 68.7%, when compared the four neighbourhoods (fig.2), and a low percentage of just 4.4% low-skilled workers. It also has relatively low values for the percentage of the population with low-studies and young people without post-compulsory education. The average annual income is just over €4000 less per year than La Dreta de l'Eixample (where school A is located), which reports the highest annual income out of the four districts.

The arrival of the Olympics in 1993, led to the regeneration and development of El Poblenou, which was previously made up of factories and industrial buildings, many of which had been abandoned. It had a largely working-class and migrant population, but began attracting middle-class professionals, expatriates, and young creatives, due to the 22@ Barcelona project in the early 2000s, which converted much of the area into a hub for technology, innovation, and creative industries and paved the way to the gentrification of the neighbourhood. It is now comprised of a mix of long-time residents of working-class background, as well as middle-class professionals and a growing international community.

Though the Small Area Socioeconomic Index for El Poblenou is the second lowest out of the 4 schools, the school reports that their student population come from mostly middle-high socioeconomic class families. They report that families tend to have a high involvement with the centre and the teaching team (more than 90% are part of the Parents' Association that collaborates closely with the centre), in addition to participating in different activities and providing economic contributions to the school. Whilst exact figures are not published, school C is made up of 2 groups per year, meaning that the number of students enrolled across early years and primary is likely to be between 400-500 students.

Schoolyard C – before transformation (current status)

Source: Authors own photos

3.3.4 School D - La Font d'en Fargues

The neighbourhood of Font d'en Fargues has the highest percentage of employment out of the four districts and the lowest percentage of foreigners from low- or middle-income countries. Compared with the other neighbourhoods, it also records a relatively low percentage of low skilled workers, low percentage of population with low education and a low percentage of young people without post-compulsory education. It also has the second highest average annual income per person out of the four districts at €19,606.20.

In the early 1900's, the area was sparsely populated, with a focus on single-family homes and large estates, of middle- and upper-class residents. The migration of the 1950's saw an increase in urbanization and densification, with more residential buildings and infrastructure, though its socio-economic status remained relatively high. Development continued through the end of the 1900's, which led to increased diversity of population moving into the area, including middle-class families and some lower-income residents. During the 2000's, the area has become more multi-cultural and its socio-economic status has remained relatively stable, with a mix residents of mostly middle and high socio-economic status. The Small Area Socioeconomic Index for this neighbourhood is the second highest out of the 4 districts studied with a value of 118.1, closely behind La Dreta de l'Eixample with 121.1.

School D's current building was constructed in 2000, as it brought together two schools that had previously served the neighbourhood. It is made up of 2 groups per year from early years to primary education. The educational direction team is relatively new, with the current directive team having take over 2 years ago and spearheading much of the efforts to innovate and develop the school and pedagogy.

Schoolyard D – before transformation (current status)

Source: Authors own photos

4. Methods

This study uses mixed methodology to evaluate and compare the physical attributes and use of four primary school playgrounds, all from different districts of Barcelona with varying socio-economic statuses. Two of the selected schools had undergone transformation to naturalise their schoolyard in the summer of 2023, and two are due to undergo transformation in the summer of 2025. Three types of data were collected from each school, two quantitative and one qualitative. Quantitative data was collected by: (1) use of a Patio Evaluation Tool to evaluate the physicality of the space, scoring it based on its level of naturalisation and, (2) use of a registration sheet to record the impact of the space, by observing play and behaviour during breaktime. Qualitative data was collected in the form of interviews. Interviews were carried out with 2 members of staff from each school: the head teacher and a member of the teaching staff.

4.1 Physical Patio Evaluation

To evaluate and compare the physical space and attributes of each schoolyard, within the context of naturalisation, I used a tool based on the Green Schoolyard Evaluation Tool (van den Bogerd & Maas, 2024), adapted for use in a Mediterranean climate (appendix D). Adaptations include allowing for fewer varieties of vegetation in smaller schoolyards, provision of drinking water and the use of a system to reuse water. Other adaptations to the tool are the inclusion of the presence of outdoor learning spaces such as an agora and it include points that consider how the maintenance of the space is used. The Naturalised Patio Evaluation Tool assesses the space based on 5 main categories:

- 1) Green and brown – measuring the quantity and variety of trees and vegetation
- 2) Design and maintenance – measuring the quantity of natural elements such as soil, sand and grass, compared to non-natural elements such as concrete and

asphalt. This category also measured flatness of the ground, places to sit as well as how maintenance of the space is organised.

- 3) Play, learning and socialising – measuring the presence of opportunities for mobility development such as balancing, swinging, jumping, as well as the presence of mobile play elements. It also measured the presence of a space outdoor learning such as an agora and how the space is used by the community (both school and neighbourhood).
- 4) Water – measuring the availability and use of water for play, learning and drinking, as well as scoring for the reuse of water including rainwater in the schoolyard.
- 5) Habitat for animals – measuring areas or elements designed for the life of insects and animal.

All evaluations were carried out while schoolyards were empty, allowing me to walk around freely to assess the schoolyard. Data for certain aspects measured on the tool, such as how the space is used by the community, or how the space is maintained, were taken from interviews, as this could not be observed.

Due to the drought water was not being used for play or learning in any of the schoolyards. Even those that had water courses, commented that in the past year and a half, after the transformation, they had been unable to use them due to the water scarcity.

4.2 Social behaviour and play observation

The impact of the space on children's play and behaviour was recorded on a registration sheet (appendix E), regarding the type of behaviour exhibited, the type of activity performed, and the composition of the observed groups. The sheet was divided into 3 main categories: behaviour, physical play and creative play, to guide the recording of student activity in a quantitative way. These three main categories were then divided into more specific subcategories, as defined in the table below (fig.3).

Type of interaction	Sub-category	Examples/ explanation
Behaviours	Onlooker	Students sat or standing to one side, watching other students, without taking part
	Conflictive	e.g. arguing or pushing
	Helping and Nurturing	Behaviours that are seen as kind, thoughtful or helpful e.g. comforting another child, helping each other with something, sharing toys, including solitary students
	Talking (with peers)	Talking with other students
	Talking (with adults)	Talking with teachers or monitors
	Hiding/ sheltered space	Occupying spaces such as corners, behind trees or bushes, inside tipis or huts or under/inside climbing apparatus.
	Other-	This space for any observed behaviours that did not fit into one of the categories listed.
Physical Play	Competitive (ball sports)	e.g. Football, basketball, handball, rugby
	Competitive (non-ball sports)	e.g. Races, tag, other types of chase and catch games.
	Risk-Taking Play (climbing, jumping)	e.g. climbing, jumping, running, balancing, hanging
	Use of equipment (swings, slides etc)	Use of any climbing frames or typical playground equipment such as swings and slides.
	Rule-Based (e.g. hopscotch)	e.g. hopscotch, hide and seek, imaginary games with a clear rule element, 'statue' games.
	Other-	Space left for any other types of physical play noted that didn't fit into the above category e.g. running that didn't appear to have a clear competitive element.
Creative play	Pretend/Imaginative (with toys)	Any type of imaginary or pretend play that includes the use of toys, made of natural or synthetic materials.
	Pretend/Imaginative (without toys)	Any type of imaginary or pretend play that includes the use of toys, made of natural or synthetic materials.
	Dramatic or Role Play	e.g. singing, performing, dancing or imaginary games where its clear students have assigned roles or characters in the game.
	Constructive	Building things, such as towers, castles, fitting things together.
	Exploratory/Sensory	Play with natural elements such as sand or vegetation.
	Rule-Based Play (e.g. cards)	e.g. cards, board games.
	Other-	Space left for any creative play types that didn't fit into the above categories.

Fig. 3 Table listing patio observation categories with examples of each

Observations were made through visual scanning of the schoolyard space. To ensure all areas of the schoolyard were observed fairly, I moved positions systematically during the observation time, to gain perspective of different areas of the schoolyard and avoid bias to one area. The number of different observation points occupied, varied depending on the size and shape of the schoolyard, as well as the number of students. Bigger schoolyards, or those with more students, were more challenging to observe fully from one position, so I moved positions more than in small schoolyards, or those with fewer students. When recording each type of interaction observed, a tally mark was recorded based on the child's estimated age and gender. Ages were grouped into 3 categories: 3-5, 6-8, 9-11). For example, if a female student that seemed to be aged around 4, was observed playing with a bucket in the sand, a tally mark would be recorded under age group '3-5' and under 'girls', for the subcategory 'Pretend/Imaginative (with toys)'. Further categories listed in types of interactions were solitary play (playing alone), parallel play (playing beside each other but not necessarily together) and collaborative play (playing together). Finally, there was a space left open for written notes on overall impressions of the use of the space, as well as detailing specific examples of the types of play or behaviours noted. All recording sheets were transferred into electronic format and are provided in the supplementary materials.

School A was observed once in January from 10:30-11:30. This is a small school with one class per year group (a total of 211 students). Here students are split into 2 groups for break time, with the younger half of the students having breaktime from 10:30-11, and the older half of students having breaktime from 11:00- 11:30. In this way, I was able to observe all ages during this 1-hour observation.

School's C and D were also observed once each in November. Both schools had just one break time for all students from 11:00-11:30, though the early years groups were separated in a different play space, and I was not able to observe the 3-5 age range for these 2 schools. Both schools are made up of 2 groups per year, and both are yet to be transformed, though school D, located in Font d'en Fargues has a larger schoolyard than school C, located in Poblenou.

School B, located in Vallbona, a deprived neighbourhood located out the outskirts of the city, had a more fragmented break time structure, which made it more difficult to arrange an observation of all year groups on the same day. The early years groups had break time between 12:30-13:00, the first 3 primary year groups had breaktime from 10:30-11:00 and the last 3 primary year groups had break time from 11:00-11:30. This is interesting to note in comparison to the other schools, as this school has a large schoolyard and reports the fewest total students (142), which make up one class per year group. Yet students are divided into the smallest groups for separate breaktimes, compared to the breaktime structure of other schools. As this school is about to expand into secondary education, it will be interesting to see how breaktimes will be reorganised to accommodate early years, primary and secondary students.

The first observation scheduled with this school in November was due to be an all-day observation of all age ranges. However, this was cancelled due to a strong wind weather alert that day. Whilst I attended the break time, students were instructed to stay under the porch and were not allowed out into the open schoolyard space. Rescheduling the observation was difficult, firstly due to scheduling changes as the Christmas break approached, and secondly due to the fragmentation of the breaktimes. Finally, I was able to arrange 2 different observations in January, one of the older primary groups between 11:00-11:30 and one of the early years' groups from 12:30-13:00.

Analysis

To analyse the observations, I created bar charts and pie charts using Canva for each category: behaviour, physical play and creative play, for each school (appendix A, B and C). I chose to use a bar chart for the age ranges to be able to compare how the different ages groups were distributed between the subcategories. I chose to do a single pie chart for girls and a single pie chart for boys, to allow me to compare the distribution of behaviours or play types in boys compared to girls.

Limitations

I was unable to organise observations covering all ages groups for all schools, which hinders the comparative analysis possible between schools. Furthermore, the study would be strengthened by multiple observations of each school, over different periods of the year, to compare how weather impacts the interactions recorded. It is also important to note that on the day of all of my observations, balls were not allowed. For schools A, B and D, this was by chance. School C never allows ball sports to be played during breaktimes. This means I was not able to observe how the option of ball impacts dynamics.

Observations for school's C and D (untransformed) and for the first half of school A (transformed) had a high number of students moving around and using the space. With so many students moving around, it was not possible to record the exact numbers of students completing each action throughout the whole break, with total accuracy. The numbers marked down serve to provide an overview of the general use of the space for comparative purposes and to identify significant trends of play or behaviour in each school. Additionally, the age of students was assumed based on a quick visual assessment, which could have led to some inaccuracies in how interactions were recorded. Furthermore, it was found that it was not possible to record the number of students engaging in parallel and collaborative play, as it was too numerous to count, whilst also recording behaviour and play types. This was recorded on the registration sheet as was marked down as TMTC (too much to count). Therefore, in most cases, only numbers for solitary play were recorded, as there were few instances of solitary play.

In contrast, the second half of the observation with school A (transformed), and both observations with school B (transformed) had a significantly reduced number of students, again impacting the power of the comparative analysis possible between observations of different schools. For school A, the reason for the reduced number of students was due to an excursion for 2 classes on that day. For school B, the low student numbers was due to illness, affecting a large number of students and teachers.

The conclusions of this study would be strengthened if further observations could be carried out for these schools, when a full cohort of students is present.

4.3 Interviews

The interviews were structured into seven themes: motivation and context for participating in the program, participative processes (in the design of the schoolyard), implementation of the schoolyard, maintenance of the new structures and vegetation, impact and use of the space (before and after transformation if relevant), pedagogic implications of the naturalised schoolyard, accessibility of the space to the neighbourhood and disadvantages communities. Most time was given to the themes of motivation and context, participative processes, impact and use and pedagogic implications.

The interviews were conducted in throughout November and December 2024 and January 2025, and lasted between 20-60 minutes, depending on the interviewee. Schools that had completed the transformation tended to offer more detailed responses. School A and school D completed a combined interview with both interviewees together. Two separate interviews were carried out for each member of staff for school B and C. Interviews were conducted in person or online via zoom, and all interviews were audio-recorded with the prior consent of the participants, and assurance that their responses would be anonymised.

Analysis

Interviews were transcribed and coded using NVivo software to identify core emerging themes. 21 core themes were identified. Figure 4 shows the different themes identified across the interviews, organised by hierarchy; larger boxes represent greater number of references. Quotes under each theme were extracted for each interview and collated into a matrix. This allowed for easier comparison between interviews and deeper analysis of responses to identify patterns in each school independently, as well as between transformed and untransformed schools.

Fig. 4 Hierarchy chart extracted from NVivo based on the core themes identified across the interviews collectively. Larger boxes and darker colours represent more frequent references of this theme.

5. Results

Full results tables and interview transcripts provided in the supplementary materials.

Schoolyard context

The table below (fig.5) summarises the physicality of each schoolyard to serve as a reference and provide context for the results detailed below.

School	District	Transformed?	Description
A	La Dreta de l'Eixample	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small schoolyard - Newly planted trees and vegetation such as bushes - Numerous play structures including huts, tipis, tubes and climbing frames - Sandy area covering about 20% of the schoolyard with moveable toys available for use with the sand
B	Vallbona	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large schoolyard - Lots of vegetation and natural surfaces - Numerous tipi, hut and mobility structures including balance beams and climbing frames - No moveable objects for play
C	El Poblenou	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mid-sized schoolyard - Very large concrete sports pitch - Exposed to the sun, with little shade - Small area of sand with some mobile play elements - Area of artificial grass lining one side of the schoolyard, with 2 play structures
D	La Font d'en Fargues	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large schoolyard - Very large concrete sports pitch - Sandy area covering about 20% of the area of the schoolyard - Sports pitch expose to the sun, sandy area under shade via natural and non-natural elements - One wooden climbing apparatus - Has a school garden

5.1 Naturalised Patio Evaluation

All completed evaluation tools can be found in full in the supplementary materials.

The Naturalised Patio Evaluation Tool allowed me to compare not only the presence and variety of natural elements, but also to evaluate the availability and variety of play mobility and learning opportunities. Figure 6 shows a summarized version of the 4 matrixes to allow for easier comparison. School A located in Dreta de l'Eixample, and school B located in Vallbona, have both been transformed through the Transformem els Patis project, and show a total score of 26 and 30 respectively. School C located in Poblenou, and school D located in Font d'en Fargues are both yet to be transformed and have both scored the same overall total of 19.

Category	Benefits for	School A score	School B score	School C score	School D score	Maximum score possible
1. Green and brown Measures the amount and variety of vegetation. Also measures the presence of plants that are useful for playing or learning vs aesthetic.	D, B, C, E, N	7	9	4	3	15
2. Design Measures the amount of natural and non-natural materials available in the space, and the presences of natural vs non-natural seats, shade. Also measures the use of the community in patio maintenance.	D, B, C, E, N	8	10	5	10	19
3. Play and learning Measures the variety of opportunities for physical and creative play with natural and non-natural materials. Also measures the availability of spaces for educational activities.	D, E, N	7	5	6	5	11
4. Water Measures presence of water for play, learning and drinking. Also measures the reuse of water resource.	D, C, E, N	4	3	1	1	7
5. Habitat for animals Measures presence of different habitats for insects and animals.	D, B, E, N	0	3	3	0	7
Total Score		26	30	19	19	59

Fig.6 Summary table of the naturalised patio assessment tool, showing the subtotal scores for the 5 subsections of the assessment, as well as the overall total for each school. The final column in yellow shows the maximum possible scores for each section. Column 2 indicates who or what may benefit from each element of the patio; D= Child development, B0 Biodiversity, C= Climate resilience, E= Co-education, N= Citizenship and neighbourhood. Full Evaluation tables for each school can be found in the supplementary materials.

5.1.1 Category 1- Green and Brown

The most notable difference between post and pre-transformation schools is in category 1: green and brown, which measures the amount and variety of vegetation, though it was noted that neither schoolyard includes vegetation for use in play or learning or edible plants. Naturalised schools A and B show a greater quantity and variety of vegetation, scoring a total of 7 and 9 points, out of a possible 15. School B in particular is notably much greener than all other schoolyards, though students are restricted from play in the vegetation. In contrast, schools C and D, which have yet to be naturalised, scored only 4 and 3 respectively.

5.1.2 Category 2- Design and Maintenance

In this category, school B which has been transformed, and D which has not been transformed, scored joint highest out of the 4 schools, with a score of 10 out of 19 each. School A which has been transformed, also scored highly, with a score of 8. A high score in the design is in line with expectations for schools A and B, as they have been recently transformed with a schoolyard design to include more natural elements (such as sand and earth as opposed to concrete or artificial surfaces), additional shade and more seated areas.

Surprisingly, school D, which has not yet been transformed, scored higher than school A which has been transformed. This score can be mostly explained by the fact, the patio has a fairly large percentage coverage of sand and earth as well as a school garden and small grassy area in one corner of the yard. The use and maintenance of the garden is currently being managed by one of the school's teachers, who has an additional role as sustainability leader, in combination with different groups of students, on a rotating basis. No other schoolyard has a school garden, and as such, does not have organised maintenance of the schoolyard. Furthermore, though the schoolyard is big and mostly exposed to the sun, they have several large trees, as well as gazebos that provide shade. Multiple moveable seating opportunities, in the way of classroom chairs, have also been provided by the school.

School C, which has not yet been transformed, scored lowest out of the four schools, with a score of 5. It has very little shade coverage and is mostly exposed to the sun, which was a key reason for them applying for the program. There is also very little coverage of natural surfaces compared to the other 3 schools, and few seating opportunities, which is reflected in their low score.

5.1.3 Category 3 - Play, learning and socialising

Schools scored similar results in this category, with schools B and D scoring 5 out of 11 and school C scoring 6 out of 11. School A scored highest in the play and learning section, despite being less green than school B and having less surface coverage of natural materials than both school B and D. The marked difference with school A compared to the other 3 schools was the availability and use of mobile materials for unguided play, as well as allowing students to autonomously interact with and explore natural elements such as vegetation, for example allowing them to pass through and play in the bushes.

It is interesting to notice that school B scores highly in the first two sections that measure the physical transformation of the space and is noticeably the greenest of all schoolyards evaluated, yet scores lowly in section 3, which measures how the space is used for play and learning. Also, despite having lots of sand and earth surface coverage, and a toy kitchen, there were no mobile elements available for students to use with those elements. In general, no mobile elements at all were noted in the schoolyard. The restricted use of the space is an indicator of how unguided play and learning may be conceptualized in this school, especially in relation to more naturalized autonomous exploration and play. It highlights how the physical presence of natural elements does not automatically lead to an enriched use of the space. Instead, physical and conceptual naturalisation exists as two independent, though connected, transformations. A final distinct difference for this school in this category compared to the others, was that the schoolyard is not open to the public, unless for extracurricular

activities held there. All other schools are part of the program 'Patis Oberts' which means open playgrounds. In this, schools open their schoolyards for the neighbourhood to use on Saturday morning. This is somewhat surprising as Vallbona, where school B is located is a historically deprived neighbourhood with a small neighbourhood community and limited public services such as parks. Perhaps it is not open due to concerns over how the space is used, monitored and maintained during the open time. This would be a point that would be interesting to investigate further with the school, to understand what their thoughts are around opening the schoolyard.

5.1.4 Category 4 - Water

Category 4, related to the presence and use of water, is limited across all schools. All have drinking water available, and none have natural water deposits for learning such as ponds. In an urban Mediterranean context, both of these results are expected given that the climate is hot and dry for much of the year. Transformed schools A and B do have water elements for play and learning available such as water course tables, however, both schools commented that they have not been able to use them due to the drought and restrictions on water use.

5.1.5 Category 5 - Habitat for animals

Finally, category 5, habitats for animals showed mixed results between schools. This shows that providing elements for insects for or other animals to utilize can be achieved regardless of the quantity of vegetation and natural materials present in a space. It also indicates that the presence of a greater variety of vegetation does not necessarily indicate that biodiversity has been considered or encouraged, possibly indicating that this is not considered as an important factor in creating greener spaces or in providing learning opportunities.

5.1.6 Key findings

- Naturalised schoolyards have a greater quantity and variety of vegetation and natural surface materials such as earth and sand.

- Naturalised schoolyards offer more structures for mobility and physical play and more sheltered spaces
- Play and learning opportunities are not directly linked to increased vegetation and natural materials, indicating that this is impacted by the school's collective intentions regarding autonomous creative play and exploration.

5.2 Observation of social and play behaviour

Graph visualisations of all observations, as referenced in the results section, can be found in the appendix given at the end of the document (appendix A, B and C)

Observations of the use of the space were separated into 3 main categories (1) behaviours, (2) physical play and (3) creative play. Activities were then recorded on the registration sheet, as they were observed, according to the characteristics of the child doing the activity i.e. if the student was a boy or a girl and which age category they belonged to. For example, if the following scenario was observed: a group of 3 boys and 2 girls, all seeming to be 9 or 10, sat talking together. This behaviour would be recorded under the subcategory 'Talking (with peers)', 5 tallies would be recorded for the age category '9-11', 3 tallies would be recorded for 'boys', and 2 for 'girls'. It is important to note that in all observations, balls were not allowed, meaning that I was unable to observe how the option of ball sports impacts breaktime dynamics.

5.2.1 School A - Transformed

This school has one class per year group and separates breaktime into 2 sessions, one for younger students, one for older students. Due to a planned excursion, 2 of the older classes were missing, meaning there were fewer students than normal. The school yard has been transformed and contains several play and sheltered structures, as well as structures for physical play, such as climbing. There is an area of sand for free play and

some vegetation, though the greenery (apart from trees) is fairly limited considering that it has been recently naturalised.

Behaviours - Figure 1, Appendix A

School A shows the greatest variety in different behaviours, out of the 3 schools. The most common observed behaviours for mid to older aged students was concentrated around talking with peers, whereas younger students favoured finding hidden or sheltered spaces, behind bushes, in corners and in huts and tipis. There were also a high number of helping and nurturing behaviours observed overall, and these behaviours were recorded for all age groups. The types of observed behaviours that were classified under this category were: including solitary students looking to join a game, sharing toys, sitting quietly with students with additional needs and comforting a student who was upset. The 'other' behaviour noted was destructive behaviour in the form of kicking the toy kitchen. However, this was momentary, and the two students quickly moved away and into another activity, without being instructed to by an adult. The distribution between genders of the observed behaviours 'Talking (with peers)' and 'Helping and nurturing' is very similar. A greater proportion of girls, compared to boys chose to occupy hidden or sheltered spaces and boys overall were observed carrying out a greater variety of behaviours than girls. However overall, the proportion of types of behaviours seen in boys compared to girls was similar.

Physical Play - Figure 5, Appendix A

School A showed most physical play in 3-5 and 6-8 age ranges, though it should also be noted there were more students overall in these age categories. Most observed physical play in general was concentrated around risk-taking play (which includes activities such as jumping, balancing and climbing) and the use of equipment (for example climbing frames, tubes, balance beams). Running was the physical activity most frequently noted in the 3-5 age range, closely followed by use of equipment and risk-taking play. The distribution of types of physical play between genders was

extremely similar, with no significant differences in physical play types in boys compared to girls.

Creative Play - Figure 9, Appendix A

School A showed significantly higher diversity of creative play types, as well as the highest number of students partaking in creative activities, than all other schools. Creative play types were noted across all age ranges, but most prominently in the 3-5 and 6-8 ages ranges. Students in the 3-5 age range showed a strong preference for exploratory/ sensory play, which a high number of students in the 6-8 age range also choosing this type of creative play. Examples of exploratory and sensory play in this school were: playing with sand, collecting rocks and leaves, and exploring the bushes. In contrast, student in the 9-11 age group were most commonly recorded in pretend/ imaginative play, creating imaginary scenarios, characters and games between themselves, as well as dancing and performing. Students in the 6-8 age range were the only ones observed in pretend/ imaginative play with toys, bar 1 boy in the 3-5 age range. The 6-8 age range showed the most even distribution across different creative play type, compared to the older and younger age groups.

The distribution of types of play between genders was similar, though a higher number of girls than boys overall chose creative play activities. The proportion of boys and girls observed in exploratory/ sensory play, constructive play, dramatic/ role play, and pretend/imaginative play (without toys) was very similar. The only category in creative play which showed a significant different between boys and girls, was in imaginative play with toys, with higher proportion of girls than boys choosing this activity.

5.2.2 School B – Transformed

This school has one class per year group and has the smallest cohort out of the 3 schools with 142 students. Despite this, students as separated into 3 groups for breaktime. It is located on the outskirts of the city, in a historically neglected neighbourhood. Out of the 4 districts, it has the lowest values for socio-economic

indicators. The schoolyard is quite large, with much of the surface covered with natural elements such as sand, grass or earth. It has the most vegetation and variety of greenery out of the schoolyards studied. Due to scheduling difficulties, I was unable to observe the younger primary groups. Due to illness, there were less students than normal attending school during the days I observed the use of the schoolyard. There were particularly few students in the early years' classes, compared to normal.

Behaviour - Figure 2, Appendix A

The most common observed behaviour in school B was talking with peers, mostly among older students. There was also a high number of students occupying hidden or sheltered spaces, such as huts, tipis and in corners of the playground that were slightly out of sight. There were some instances of helping and nurturing behaviours recorded, with students comforting a student that had fallen over and hurt themselves.

There was very similar percentage distribution of behaviour types observed in girls and boys. Though double the number female students compared to male students were recorded using sheltered spaces, this does not greatly affect the proportions, as more girls than boy were recorded in the behaviour category in general.

Physical Play - Figure 6, Appendix A

Students in school B showed a variety physical play types across all categories, minus ball sports as no balls were allowed. The most popular physical activity was running (in the 9-1 age range) and risk-taking play such as climbing, jumping and balancing. The competitive activity observed was a chase and catch game between 4 students, and the rule-based game observed was a calm game of ping pong.

The most distinct difference between physical play type observed in boys compared to girls was in risk-taking play and use of equipment, with significantly more girls choosing these activities than boys. 11 out of the 25 instances of physical play recorded in girls was risk-taking play, whereas only instance was recorded in boys.

Creative Play - Figure 10, Appendix A

Considering the number of students in the observations for school B, there was a fair amount of creative play observed, though of limited variety of play types. In contrast to school A, creative play in school B was more highly recorded in the older age group rather than the younger one, with little exploratory/ sensory play and no imaginative play with toys observed. Most of instances of creative play recorded were in the categories of pretend/imaginative without toys and dramatic/ role play. Students were observed creating and practicing dances, as well as playing imaginary games in groups. Dramatic/ role play activity, including dancing, was noted more in boys than girls, whereas girls were observed engaging in more pretend/ imaginative play, and showed the only instance of exploratory play noted.

The lack of exploratory and play with toys by the younger age group, may be in part be explained by a lack of students compared to school A. However, it is also consistent with the fact that there were no mobile toys or objects observed in the schoolyard. Whilst there was a toy kitchen and a sand pit, there were no objects to use with those play elements, limiting possibility for imaginative play with toys, constructive play and exploratory/sensory play. Furthermore, it was observed that students were called away from the vegetation when it looked like they were too close to it, or possibly trying to play with it. The only instance of exploratory play noted, was in one student who used the plastic tray that was part of the toy kitchen, to try to dig in the sand.

5.2.3 School C – Untransformed

This school is made up of 2 classes per year group and has a mid-sized schoolyard. Early years students are separated with their own patio area, but all primary students have their breaktime together in the same space. The schoolyard is made up of mostly concrete sports court, which is totally exposed to the sun. there is a small area of compact sand, and some artificial grass, with a few play structures and mobile elements, but very little seating.

Behaviour - Figure 3, Appendix A

Students in school C showed a strong preference for talking with and hiding behaviours, particularly among the older age group, 9-11 years old. Though there were few sheltered spaces, many students squeezed in and around and under the tipi and climbing frame area, which were the only sheltered spaces available in the patio. The percentage distribution of behaviour types between girls and boys is extremely close.

Physical Play - Figure 7, Appendix A

School C showed a high number of students engaged in physical play, which was mostly distributed between competitive non-ball sports, risk taking play and the use of equipment and apparatus (such as huts, climbing frames and slides). In this case the competitive activity was mostly tag (chase and catch game). This could also be classified under 'other-running' however, I chose to classify it as competitive in this observation as there was a clear competitive element. In contrast, in schools A and B, where there was also a lot of running observed, most of it didn't seem to have the same clear competitive element, rather it seemed to be running together to different points of the schoolyard or as part of an imaginary game.

The distribution of physical play types between genders was very close again. However, there was a higher proportion of boys who were observed in competitive chase and catch games, and more girls were seen using playground equipment such as the climbing frame and slide.

Creative Play - Figure 11, Appendix A

There was very little creative play observed in school C, with only 8 instances observed in total, the least out of all schools. More boys than girls were observed engaging in creative play, and boys were seen engaging in more types of creative play than girls. The creative play observed used mobile wooden planks, in the form of big dominoes and logs. Some students were using the wooden planks as balance beams, together with the logs, others were using the planks to dig in the sand, and two boys used those same

objects to create a pivot that they were using to project objects into the air.

5.2.4 School D – Untransformed

This school is made up of 2 classes per year group. The early years classes are separated into a different area for breaktime, and all primary students have their breaktime together in the main playground. The schoolyard is large and is comprised of a large concrete sports court exposed to the sun. There is also about 15-20% of the schoolyard that is covered with sand, though there were no toys provided to play with the sand on the day of the observation. Tall trees and gazebos provide shade over the sandy and seating areas. There is one climbing apparatus and several seating options provided. There is also a school garden in one corner of the schoolyard.

Behaviour - Figure 4, Appendix A

School D showed a strong preference for talking with peers' behaviour. Out of the 57 instances of behaviour noted, 49 were talking with peers. A greater number of students were engaged in this type of activity, than any other. There was some hiding behaviour observed, but as it was a very open schoolyard, there were very little sheltered spaces for students to occupy. In terms of percentage distribution of the observed behaviours between boys and girls, this was extremely similar.

Physical Play - Figure 8, Appendix A

In contrast to the other schools, only competitive non-ball sports and risk-taking behaviour observed in the physical play category. Although there was a climbing structure, students were unable to use it as it was being used as a place to sit. Several students made attempts to climb on it but were blocked by students sitting and talking on it, occupying the equipment. The competitive non-ball sport activities observed were chase and catch games, and the use of a plastic bottle as a football, to try to score goals. There was very little running and movement in the schoolyard in general, students were mostly sitting quietly and talking. Of the four schools, this observation as

a whole was notably the more subdued than others, which all had more movement and activity.

This may be explained by the fact that there were very limited elements or structures available for play in the patio. Other than the climbing structure, which was occupied by students sitting and talking on it, the only other structures available for students were tables and chairs. It should be noted that the schoolyard activity allocated for this day was that students were allowed to bring a toy from home to play with, however only 4 students were observed with toys. Perhaps on other days, other elements are provided for students to play with, and more play activity may be observed on these days.

Creative Play - Figure 12, Appendix A

School D also showed a very low number of students engaging in creative play, though more than school C. The creative play observed was pretend/ imaginative games with and without toys, as well as what appeared to be a rule-based imaginative game. The toys used were brought by the students themselves from home and there were no available materials for creative play provided. Creative play in this school was observed exclusively in boys.

5.2.5 Key findings

- Naturalised (transformed) schoolyards provide a richer environment for creative and physical play than untransformed schoolyards. Greater opportunities for different types of play, lead to a greater number of students observed engaging in a variety of physical and creative activities.
- Out of the 3 behaviour and activity categories, it is creative play showed the greatest difference between naturalised and unnaturalised schools (A and B vs C and D). This is particularly significant as schools C and D have a much greater number of students than schools A and B. Despite this, a far greater number of students were observed engaging in creative play were observed in schools A and B, which have both been naturalised.

- Creative play was seen most significantly in school A, despite it having less natural elements, such as sand and vegetation, than school B. This indicates that the amount of creative play students engage in, depends also on the mentality toward autonomous and explorative play and culture and context of the school itself.
- The distribution of the types of activities that boys engage in, compared to girls was generally balanced across all schools and activity types, bar a few minor exceptions. Despite the big differences between the 4 schools, the commonality between them was that balls were not allowed during breaktime. This suggests, that removing ball sports can significantly impact the distribution of the types of activities that boys and girls take part in, allowing for more equal play opportunities.
- Whilst the types of play and behaviour were fairly equally distributed between boys and girls in all schools, naturalised schools showed greater interaction and playing of girls and boys together. Unnaturalised schoolyards showed a great separation between boys and girls.

5.3 Interviews

The analysis of the interviews carried out revealed various themes as shown below in figure 7. Looking at all 4 schools together, the most common themes discussed were diversity of play, patio for learning, behavioural changes, wants or needs and participative processes. Comparing the highest number of coding references identified in interviews for school pre- and post-transformation, we can see some key differences. For example, transformed schools show 7 references to calm spaces, compared to just 2 in untransformed schools. Participative processes are also mentioned 13 times in interviews with schools A and B, compared to 7 in interviews with schools C and D. This is likely because schools C and D were right at the beginning of the participative processes with Transformem els Patis, so they did not have as many experiences to discuss as schools A and B, who had already completed the entire process and were now able to discuss it more in depth. Another expected result is ‘wants and needs’ being referenced more than double the amount in untransformed schools compared to

the transformed ones. One code was referenced only in transformed schools, social cohesion. This code ties in closely with behavioural changes, which are referenced strongly in both subgroups of schools, but more so in transformed schools. Vegetation and naturalising spaces, as well as diversity of play, is also referenced notably more in schools' post-transformation, compared to those pre-transformation.

Codes	Number of coding references		
	All schools	Transformed schools	Untransformed schools
Codes\\Behavioural changes	25	15	10
Codes\\Calm spaces	9	7	2
Codes\\Community use of patio	10	4	6
Codes\\Concrete, sports court	12	5	7
Codes\\Conflictive behaviour	7	2	5
Codes\\Creative activities	3	2	1
Codes\\Cultural shift	10	3	7
Codes\\Difficulty	13	6	7
Codes\\Diversity of play	34	20	14
Codes\\Maintenance	11	7	4
Codes\\Participative processes	20	13	7
Codes\\Patio for learning	31	14	17
Codes\\Pre-transformation use of space	9	3	6
Codes\\Risk taking activities	8	2	6
Codes\\Shade	15	9	6
Codes\\Social cohesion	10	10	0
Codes\\Vegetation, naturalizing spaces	16	10	6
Codes\\Want or Need	21	6	15

Fig. 7 Table comparing the number of references for each code for all schools combined vs transformed and untransformed schools. Interview data collected and coded by me. Coding references extracted from NVivo and collated manually.

5.3.1 Naturalised schools (A and B)

School A were extremely positive in their experience with the transformation process and the result they have achieved. They made several comments throughout the interview commenting on how pleased they were with the schoolyard and the impact it has had on the school community.

'In the end I think the patio we have is fantastic and great... it was a success to be able to enter this program.' - School A

The principal change they were most pleased with, was the social cohesion they have managed to achieve between different classes and levels in the school, that previously was impossible. Now having a more varied schoolyard, they comment that all students

are now able to find their own part of the schoolyard that they can enjoy. They note there are less conflicts, previously generated by football, and that they see greater inclusion and less polarisation, as previously students were either engaging in balls sports, or standing around the outside, trying to avoid being hit by balls. They see a greater richness in types of play students engage in and more interaction between students of different ages and genders, which was one of their biggest objectives.

One area they note some difficulty with, is the maintenance of the schoolyard. They have not yet decided how this will be managed, now that the government support post-transformation has ended. The trees and areas of bushes have an automatic watering system, so that is not an issue, but in one area of bushes, unwanted plants and weeds are starting to grow. Their use of the patio for outdoor learning, is limited at the moment. The occasions of its use for learning are mostly to sit outside and read or eat breakfast on the steps. They note that reflection and work needs to be done internally in the school community, to take full advantage of the space and realise the potential learning opportunities the schoolyard can now offer.

‘tenemos que cambiar un poco el chip nosotros ¿no? el patio como espacio de aprendizaje, para reflexionar’

‘We have to change our chip a little, right? the playground as a learning space, to reflect’

- School A

When asked about what the barriers were (or what they might be) to taking advantage of using the schoolyard as a space for learning, the schools listed firstly, needing a diverse and naturalised schoolyard to inspire ideas. They also listed the need for more time in the teacher’s schedule dedicated to planning, the need for breaking down barriers in mentality, to think outside of the box and as well as individual interest, creativity and desire to try something new.

School B, which has also been naturalised through the program Transformem Els Patis, also spoke very positively about the process as a whole. They commented that there were some propositions they were very unsure about at first, namely the introduction of

vegetation. They were worried firstly about if trees, bushes and other plants would survive, and if they would be difficult to maintain. They were also concerned about the types of flowers or fruits the plants may produce in case the younger students ingested them. However, after discussions with the architects and government representatives involved in the program, they opened up, compromised and found a design they were all happy with. They felt supported and listened to throughout the process. They have commented that their fears regarding the vegetation have now disappeared, and they are very happy they put their trust in the external representatives that supported them through the process. They also note that they have taught the students not to play in or damage the plants and to respect them. During the observation, I also noted one instance of breacktime supervisors calling students away from the bushes.

'The irrigation is very well prepared. The areas are very well located'... 'There has been no problem with the plants either. They grow on their own, they are born, that is, there is no problem'... 'They were very well chosen and the truth is that we were happy right away.' -

School B

Similarly to school A, school B noted less conflict and more fluidity between students in the schoolyard. With the greater variety in for activity and play, different students are drawn together due to an interest in the same activity, rather than because they have no choice other than to occupy a particular available space, as before.

In relation to using the schoolyard for learning, school B report that they currently use the space for: projects investigating trees and plants, drawing in art classes, reading, investigating light and shadow and looking for food for the class stick insects. The youngest groups also use the schoolyard for spontaneous educational moments that arise, for example planting apple seeds. One of the interviewees notes that children are more inspired and their curiosity has been sparked, and that now they enjoying looking for insects and flowers, collecting pinecones and asking questions about what they find. One difficulty noted in using the schoolyard for outdoor learning, is that the patio is in use for most of the day due to the organisation of break times (students are split into 3 separate break times plus the lunch break). This makes it difficult to find quiet

moments to go down and use the space without compromising other students' opportunity to use the space freely during their break time.

5.3.2 Un-naturalised schools (C and D)

At the time of interview, schools C and D were right at the start of the transformation process and had only had 1 group planning session. Both schools express some tensions in these starting moments of the design process and expressed a resistance giving too much priority to the inclusion of vegetation, something which was mirrored in school B at the start of their design process.

School C was concerned about not wanting to reduce the sports pitch too much, explaining that, for one part removing concrete is expensive, so the more they remove, the less budget they have for other things. For another part, they explain that their schoolyard is relatively small, and the pitch space is useful for school community gatherings, extra-curricular activities as well as physical education.

School D express concern over the maintenance that would be involved if they include more trees and other vegetation, seeing as they've had difficulties maintain the small allotment currently in one corner of their schoolyard. They also question which factors they consider to be highest priority or need for their school and where they would like to direct the budget, which would be more around climbing and play equipment and creating areas of calm and connection. Interestingly, they comment that the neighbourhood is very built-up and has little green spaces and explain that for that reason, the students are not naturally so interested or curious in natural elements. They comment that it is difficult to incorporate learning with or from nature, if the school is located in such an urban setting. Despite this, they comment that adding vegetation is not a main priority for them.

'The possibilities offered by the forest for learning, for working in the classroom, are very different from those we have here' – school D

'If there are [already] difficulties in maintaining the garden ... it's just a matter of prioritizing... we would love for shrubs or plants in the yard to be one of the priorities, but now the [priorities] are different' - School D

When asked about what the obstacles were, or may be in the future, for using the schoolyard as a space for learning, they commented that they believed it was simply a matter of creativity and desire of the individual teacher, rather than a need for specific resources or training. This indicates that they believe that taking advantage of using the schoolyard for outdoor learning will depend on a cultural shift in the mentality around pedagogy, more than just the transformation of the space itself.

'In the end, it is a matter of creativity that, of desire. So, yes, of course, we will give orientations, we will give ideas, we will give guidelines, and from there, let each teacher see if it is necessary or not. I think it is more a question of attitude than of training. - School D

Both schools have already removed ball sports from day-to-day use during breaktimes and commented on the huge impact that has had on reducing conflict. School C have totally prohibited balls during breaktime and have provided some other elements, such as mobile large wooden dominoes, a tipi and a climbing frame. School D have attempted a total conceptual transformation of breaktime. Each day of the week is designated a particular type of activity, of which all suggestions were chosen through a participative process including students and teachers. Thursday is sport day, and the final Thursday of each month, ball sports are allowed, so they provide all different types of sports balls. On another day of the week, they are allowed to bring a toy from home to play with. They note that now, even on the days ball sports are allowed, the students are far more able to regulate themselves and their emotions and they don't see the same conflicts that they used to around football for example. Creating calm spaces, where students and sit and talk was stressed as a key priority for school D during the interview and they are working towards helping students to be able to self-regulate their emotions.

'That first commitment [to change] at a conceptual level has already made the uses and dynamics of the playground much more than co-educational' – School D

'Space affects our emotions and these affect learning and that this positively affects or reverses learning. That is, that they can arrive at class after being in the playground in the morning or at noon, more concentrated, with a more attentive communicative capacity, more active, to be able to work better' – School D

For school C, the principal priority is to increase shade. The expressed a strong desire for an agora where they can hold assemblies, performances and use it for creative arts, which is an important focus for this school. When asking what the students were asking for most, the school commented that the children were asking most of shade and an agora. I noticed this as quite different to the other schools, who all mentioned students coming up with wild ideas, such as swimming pools and animals. I found it unusual that the students in this school were not also asking for imaginative things.

5.3.3 Key findings

- All schools report that the removal of balls and ball sports has dramatically reduced the number of conflicts between students, some noting a positive impact on students coming into class in a calmer mindset.
- Transformed schools report a greater cohesion, fluidity and equity between students. However this is a lot more pronounced in school A, who have changed their breaktime structure to bring students of different ages together more.
- Transformed schools report a greater variety of activities noticed in the students. School B specifically notes a curiosity from the early years groups in natural elements including plants and insects that they find in the schoolyard. This is significant as this schoolyard is the greenest and most natural out of the 4 schools.

- School B, located in a deprived neighbourhood, is the only one that reports using the schoolyard for outdoor learning in a variety of different ways, across different year groups and in different types of subjects. They also report spontaneous outdoor investigations, initiated by student's questions, in the early years group. This is the only school that talks in depth about outdoor learning and puts a focus on it. School D expresses some use of outdoor learning, however in comparison to school B, no other school seems to be giving thought and consideration into how to integrate the outdoors in learning and pedagogy.
- Whilst there is a desire for transformation, there is a resistance to greening within the transformation. Both schools currently in the design process, express a resistance to adding a lot of vegetation, either for reasons of long-term maintenance, a lack of interest, or in order to keep a significant sports court space for school parties and extra-curricular or physical education activities. School B also discuss their resistance to greening at the beginning of their process, but comment on how pleased they were to have listened to the advice of the architects and the city council representatives, that encouraged them to include more vegetation. They have noted that none of their initial reasons for resisting the greening, have ended up becoming a problem.

6. Discussion

Looking collectively at the results from the physical patio evaluation, break time observation and interviews for the four schools, it is clear that a more naturalised schoolyard offers a richer diversity of play and learning opportunities, reduces conflict and allows for more social cohesion and interaction; a conclusion which has also been reported in a recently published pilot evaluation of the Transformem els Patis program, which evaluated schoolyard use, social interaction, physical activity, and diversity of play in transformed and untransformed schools (Periañez et al., 2024).

Greatest social cohesion was noted in school A, and it was clear in their interview that this was a core outcome they wanted to achieve with the transformation. In contrast, school B separates students into 3 separate break times, allowing for less opportunities of interaction between different parts of the school and leading to students being more dispersed in a large schoolyard, potentially further limiting interactions. Drawing from my own years of experience as a teacher in schools with challenging behaviour, separating students into smaller groups is sometimes used as a technique for behavioural control. On the other hand, having more space per student could offer a greater opportunity for students to explore and use the space. So, whilst a naturalised schoolyard provides greater opportunities for social development, lessening boundaries between children of different ages and gender, my results suggest that for the greatest impact there also needs to be a conceptual intention, led from the top, in the school community as a whole; supporting the idea that a Whole School Approach is needed for effective change.

My results also show that a naturalised schoolyard promotes creative play, as shown by the extremely limited creative play observed in schools C and D in comparison to schools A and B. A diversity in environment provides children opportunities for sensory, exploratory and imaginary play. Whilst schools C and D have largely removed ball sports, there is little other stimulation for them. This is particularly evident in school D,

which has just one climbing frame and the rest of the space is a large exposed concrete sports pitch or a sandy area with chairs and tables laid out and protected by awnings. School A showed the greatest quantity and variety of creative, despite the fact that School B scored highest overall in the Naturalisation Evaluation Tool and is made up of more natural elements and vegetation. Due to the presence of mobile elements and allowing students to play in and behind the vegetation, school A scored higher than school B in the play and learning category, despite school B's schoolyard containing a much higher proportion of natural elements and vegetation. This highlights the relevance of Loose Parts Theory in creating rich environments for play, learning and development as was also reported by Spencer et al. 2019 in their report on education perceptions on the benefits and challenges of loose parts play in outdoor environments. Perhaps one of the reasons why school A provided a richer opportunity for creative and unguided play with loose elements and vegetation, despite having less green coverage overall, is due to the individual school culture and ethos. Something which can be impacted by many different factors, including school size, geographical situation, the socio-economic status of the area and the families who attend the school. With school B separating students over 3 separate breaktimes, as well as not providing mobile elements, it suggests that perhaps that students behaviour is more carefully controlled, and they are less willing to allow students to explore and use elements autonomously. This inference is further supported by the fact that the first scheduled observation with this school was cancelled due to strong wind alerts. This indicated that there is a discomfort in this school, around uncontrolled, wild experiences.

Although there is a clear discomfort in wild exploration, school B is the only school that referenced the use of the patio for outdoor learning in a meaningful way, and it was noted by the head teacher that was one of the key reasons they wanted to Transform their schoolyard. They are utilising the outside to study science, art and to read or simply take class outdoors and make use of the calming effect of spending time outside and around nature. Furthermore, they are using the schoolyard for spontaneous explorations and investigations led by student's curiosity. It is significant that the greenest school, with the most natural elements, is the one where pedagogy has been most transformed, and children's curiosity has been sparked.

However, school A which has also been transformed does not make the same use of the schoolyard for learning, currently using it just for reading, though they express a desire to make more use of it for learning. Schools C and D also make little reference to using the schoolyard for learning, apart from using it for reading or for assemblies and workshops. At least in the context of greening their schoolyard, for these schools, vegetation and natural elements do not seem to be considered as critical elements to enrich day to day learning. However, as evidenced by school B, it can be a place of curiosity, inspiration, investigation and learning. In this school, they seem to be moving towards embodying Wild Pedagogies, challenging rigid teaching boundaries and taking advantage of spontaneous and unexpected moments and exploring the space you have available to find nature and whatever learning opportunities may be found (Jickling et al., 2024) .

As an interviewee from school A said, to integrate the schoolyard and nature itself as a place of learning we have to ‘change our chip’ and break down our learning understanding of what is learning and what is the right way to teach. As schools in a densely populated city, that have likely had concrete schoolyards for a very long time, if not forever, it is not easy to imagine how outdoor learning and learning from natural elements, can be integrated into the everyday. Schools C and D both expressed their concern with adding lots of vegetation, as did school B at the start of their process. And now, after nearly 2 years working with a greener schoolyard they have embraced it as a place of learning. What is missing across all schools, which would allow them to realise the educational benefits a green schoolyard can offer, is touchstone one of Wild Pedagogies, decentering the learning process and reimagining our relationship with nature (Jickling et al., 2024).

Periañez et al., 2024 talk about the 3 layers of the schoolyard environment, which determine how it is used and the activities and social interactions you observe there. There is the physical or built environment (structures and physical characteristics of the space), the social environment (people to interact with), and the cultural environment (established norms and restrictions). This is reflected in the results of my study, in the way that creative play and social cohesion was so much more prevalent in school A

compared to the others, that school D's students were so much more subdued than all the other schools, and that outdoor learning is only being integrated in a significant way in school B. What seems to have been a leading factor for each of these core defining observations is an intention which has been set by the educational team, in wanting to achieve that outcome. Therefore, whilst a physical transformation of naturalising schoolyards can provide an incredible opportunity for the transformation of play (creative and physical), social interaction and pedagogy; without a cultural and conceptual shift in regard to the use and value of natural elements and spaces are conceptualised, the impact of the changes will not be as significant or transformative as they could be. To redefine pedagogy and naturalise education within the state schooling system, is challenging and takes time, and naturalising schoolyards is a promising and critical step in working toward achieving a meaningful and profound transformation in the educational system.

This study is limited in respect to the amount of data recorded. Only 1 observation was done for each school and two people interviewed. For a more comprehensive analysis of the use of the space and the impact of the transformations, it would be useful to repeat observations through the school year and ensuring all age groups are recorded at each school on that day. In that way, the comparison between schools can be stronger and more representative. It will also allow for a view of how the use of the patio may change throughout different parts of the year, as the seasons changes. To strengthen our understanding the long-term impact and benefits of naturalising schoolyards, further studies are needed, on more schools in different contexts and at different parts of the naturalisation process. It would be especially significant if long term studies were carried out, following the same schools over a number of years, allowing us to follow the evolution of the transformation process, and gain a more profound understanding. Further work also needs to be done on how schools and educators can be supported to redefine the conceptualisation of the schoolyard, to integrate nature as a co-educator and overcome the barriers that prevent its potential as a space of learning, from being realised.

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Appendix

A. Visualisations of observed behaviour

Fig. 1 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different behaviours observed in different age groups in school A. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances were observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 2 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different behaviours observed in different age groups in school B. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances were observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 3 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different behaviours observed in different age groups in school C. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances were observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 4 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different behaviours observed in different age groups in school D. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances were observed in boys and girls.

B. Visualisations of observed physical play

Fig. 5 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of physical play observed in different age groups in school A. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 6 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of physical play observed in different age groups in school B. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 7 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of physical play observed in different age groups in school C. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 8 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of physical play observed in different age groups in school D. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

C. Visualisations of observed creative play

Fig. 9 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of creative play observed in different age groups in school A. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 10 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of creative play observed in different age groups in school B. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 11 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of creative play observed in different age groups in school C. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

Fig. 12 On the left is a bar chart showing the number of instances different types of creative play observed in different age groups in school D. On the right, 2 pie charts show the distribution of those instances observed in boys and girls.

D. Naturalised Patio Evaluation Tool

Renaturalized patios evaluation tool

130 / 5.000
 *Beneficial for D: Child development; B: Biodiversity; C: Climate resilience; E: Co-education; V: Citizenship and neighborhood

School Name:	Date and hour:
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Categoria	Item number	Item definition	*Benefits for:	Scale	Score
1. Green and brown	1.1	Fraction or percentage of yard with vegetation such as herbs, shrubs, and trees (includes garden area).	D, B, C, E, V	0=none or practically non-existent on the floor or walls; 1=1/5 of the yard or less than 20% of the yard; 2=2/5 parts of the patio or between 21% and 40%; 3=3/5 parts of the yard or between 41% and 60%; 4=4/5 of the yard or between 61% and 80%; 5=almost the entire yard, including walls, or more than 81%.	
	1.2	Types of vegetation in the yard:			
		(a) There are trees, which have 1 or more trunks	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(b) There are shrubs, which are woody plants that branch from the ground	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(c) There is ground-covering vegetation consisting of low-growing grasses and flowers without a woody stem	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	1.3	(d) There are vertical walls of herbaceous vegetation	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		Variety of vegetation (consider variation in size, color, smell, texture, fruit, flowers, deciduous and perennial):			
		(a) There is variety in the selection of trees (minimum 2 different ones in a small yard and 5 in a large yard)	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	1.4	(b) There is variety in the selection of shrubs (minimum 2 different ones in a small yard and 5 in a large yard)	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(c) There is variety in the selection of herbs (minimum 2 different in a small yard and 5 in a large yard)	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
The vegetation planted in the yard does not follow only aesthetic criteria, but is designed for children to play with		D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
1.5	There is vegetation for edible or medicinal uses such as a vegetable garden, aromatic garden, fruit trees or shrubs with edible berries (non-toxic)	D, B, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
2. Design	2.1	Fraction or percentage of the ground surface that consists of natural cover such as grass, sand, soil, bark, cork, salon, etc.	D, B, C, E, V	0=none or almost none; 1=1/5 of the yard or less than 20% of the yard; 2=2/5 parts of the patio or between 21% and 40%; 3=3/5 parts of the yard or between 41% and 60%; 4=4/5 of the yard or between 61% and 80%; 5=almost the whole yard or more than 81%.	
	2.2	Variety of natural surfaces:			
		(a) There is grass, meadow (artificial does not count)	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(b) There is sand	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(c) There is hall	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(d) Scotch or cork or similar is present	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	2.3	(e) Others (gravel, stone, pebbles, etc.)	D, B, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		There is a flat surface (not paved) where children can gather for play and learning activities	D, E	0=No; 1=Yes	
	2.4	There are different unevenness in the ground such as hills or pits	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	2.5	There are hide-and-peek areas for children where they can play independently out of sight of adults, such as bushes, a large tree, a cabin	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
2.6	There are "natural" places to sit (not tables with chairs) like a tree trunk or a rock	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
2.7	There are non-"natural" seating (not tables with chairs) such as tables and chairs	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		

	2.8	There are shaded areas made of natural materials, including trees, pergolas, huts, etc.	D, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
3. Play and learning	3.1	There are multiple opportunities for children's mobility:			
		(a) Climbing or scrambling	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(b) Jump	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(c) To balance	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(d) Swing	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(e) Rolling	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	(f) Running	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
3.2	Children can use sand, soil, sand, bark, during play and learning (eg they have a sandbox)	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
3.3	There are mobile natural materials, such as logs, wood, branches, straw, which do not have a specific purpose and which can be moved, adapted, modified and manipulated by children	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
3.4	There are moving non-natural materials, such as fabrics, ropes, pipes, buckets, leads, lids etc. which do not have a specific purpose and which can be moved, adapted, modified and manipulated by children.	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
3.5	There is an agora or similar	D, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
4. Water	4.1	There are water features that children can use to drink, play and learn, such as fountains, streams, water bowls, water tables, etc.	D, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	4.2	The water element is combined with other natural elements such as stones, sand, salt...	D, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	4.3	Rainwater is used in the yard:			
		(a) the drainage is visibly disconnected to form basins	D, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(b) water is visibly diverted by means of watercourses	D, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
	(c) pond or similar containment elements for play and learning	D, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
4.4	There is a system to avoid wasting water or reusing rainwater or spring water (pipes, tap device, buckets, deposits for collecting rainwater...)	D, C, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes		
5. Habitat for animals	5.1	Zones or elements enabled for the life of insects and animals:			
		(a) Insect hotels (including butterflies and bees)	D, B, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(b) Nest houses	D, B, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(c) Messy or compound spaces	D, B, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(d) Wooden fences	D, B, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	
		(e) Feeders for birds or other animals	D, B, E, V	0=No; 1=Yes	

E. Use of patio- observation recording sheet

Type of interaction	Sub-category	No. of students (by age range)			No. of students (by gender)	
		3-5	6-8	9-11	Boys	Girls
Behaviours	Onlooker					
	Conflictive					
	Helping and Nurturing					
	Talking (with peers)					
	Talking (with adults)					
	Hiding/ sheltered space					
	Other-					
Physical Play	Competitive (ball sports)					
	Competitive (non-ball sports)					
	Risk-Taking Play (climbing, jumping)					
	Use of equipment (swings, slides etc)					
	Rule-Based (e.g. hopscotch)					
	Other-					
Creative play	Pretend/Imaginative (with toys)					
	Pretend/Imaginative (without toys)					
	Dramatic or Role Play					
	Constructive					
	Exploratory/Sensory					
	Rule-Based Play (e.g. cards)					
Other-						
Solitary						
Parallel/ associative						
Cooperative						

Other observations e.g. Was there play between different age groups? What was the gender distribution and interaction in different areas?

F. Interview question sheet

For school pre- transformation

Ambitos	Preguntas
Motivation and context (10 min max)	<p>Podemos comenzar con un poco de historia anterior del proyecto Transformem, brevemente, ¿por qué su escuela se comprometió con el proceso de cambio del patio escolar?</p> <p>(Trigger points, if needed or not covered above: ¿Hubo algunos precedentes, intentos previos o alguna ocurrencia/anécdota del pasado que le gustaría compartir en relación con la necesidad de tener patios más verdes, jugables, inclusivos y adaptados al cambio climático?)</p> <p>Esto en relación con vuestra motivación de participar/iniciar el proyecto.</p>
Participation (5-8min)	<p>¿Ya habéis completado los procesos participativos?</p> <p>En caso afirmativo... ¿podría contar un poco sobre el proceso de participación: como fue?</p> <p>(Trigger points: qué actividades se organizaron a nivel de la escuela en las diferentes etapas, quién las organizó, cómo fue la participación (quién participó)?</p> <p>¿Que pidieron mas las niñas y niños? Que se decidió al final?</p> <p>¿Que son los puntos más importantes para la escuela en el diseño del patio?</p> <p>Y una cosa: aunque esto es un poco complicado, pero antes del comienzo de los procesos participativos, habéis hecho alguna actividad alrededor de los patios verdes, diversos, vivos, para que las niñas y niños estén concienciadas con los objetivos del programa, digamos?</p>
Maintenance (5min)	<p>¿Habéis pensado en cómo se organizará el mantenimiento de toda la vegetación e instalaciones nuevas? (qué personas) ¿Lo harán voluntariamente, o remunerado?</p> <p>¿El tema de mantenimiento ha influido las decisiones sobre diseño?</p> <p>¿Sabe si vais a recibir ayuda para el mantenimiento?</p> <p>¿Se planificó la necesidad de hacer el mantenimiento en la fase inicial de diseño?</p>
Impact and use (10)	<p>¿Cuáles son vuestras impresiones del uso actual del patio por parte del alumnado, por ejemplo en respeto a si hay grupos o actividades en</p>

	<p>particular que domina en espacio? Qué grupos y a qué horas usan el espacio (solo durante el recreo o también para hacer clase)?</p> <p>¿Cuales son los cambios que esperas notar en los niños? Por ejemplo, en la interacción social, juego, desarrollo emocional, desarrollo cognitivo, capacidad de atención, cuidado de plantas/insectos</p>
Pedagogic implications (10)	<p>¿Crees que el “nuevo” patio puede ser un espacio de enseñanza y aprendizaje de contenidos y competencias curriculares?</p> <p>(Trigger questions: ¿Hay planes de utilizarlo para clases al aire libre?</p> <p>¿Pensáis que el profesorado necesitaría un poco mas de formación sobre enseñanza en el patio, o las zonas exteriores? Habrá interés si se ofrece ese topo de formaciones?</p>
Accessibility and justice considerations (5 mins)	<p>¿Estará abierto el patio en horarios fuera de los lectivos? ¿Para quién?</p> <p>¿Para qué tipos de actividades?</p>
Concluding remarks (5mins)	<p>¿Se te ocurre algo importante alrededor de la gobernanza de su patio escolar que no hemos abordado? ¿Alguna anécdota o recomendación sobre el empieza de la experiencia que te gustaría compartir al final?</p>

For schools post- transformation

Ambitos	Preguntas
Motivation and context (10 min max)	<p>Podemos comenzar con un poco de historia anterior del proyecto Transformem, brevemente, ¿por qué su escuela se comprometió con el proceso de cambio del patio escolar?</p> <p>(Trigger points, if needed or not covered above: ¿Hubo algunos precedentes, intentos previos o alguna ocurrencia/anécdota del pasado que le gustaría compartir en relación con la necesidad de tener patios más verdes, jugables, inclusivos y adaptados al cambio climático?)</p> <p>Esto en relación con vuestra motivación de participar/iniciar el proyecto.</p>
Participation (5-8min)	<p>Entonces, ¿podría contar un poco sobre el proceso de participación: como fue?</p> <p>(Trigger points: qué actividades se organizaron a nivel de la escuela en las diferentes etapas, quién las organizó, cómo fue la participación (quién participó)?</p> <p>Que pidieron mas las niñas y niños? Que se decidió al final¿</p>

	<p>¿cuáles fueron los puntos más importantes para la escuela en el diseño del patio?</p> <p>Y una cosa: aunque esto es un poco complicado, pero antes del comienzo de los procesos participativos, habéis hecho alguna actividad alrededor de los patios verdes, diversos, vivos, para que las niñas y niños estén concienciadas con los objetivos del programa, digamos?</p>
Implementation (5min)	<p>¿Cómo fue la implementación(las obras)? ¿Cuánto tiempo duraron las obras en el patio? ¿Algún obstáculo importante? ¿Qué fue lo más difícil?</p> <p>¿Hasta que punto la transformación encaja con sus expectativas de la transformación?</p>
Maintenance (5min)	<p>¿Cómo se organiza el mantenimiento de toda la vegetación e instalaciones nuevas? (qué personas) ¿Lo hacen voluntariamente, o remunerado?</p> <p>¿Que tipo de ayuda recibís para el mantenimiento?</p> <p>¿Se planificó la necesidad de hacer el mantenimiento en la fase inicial de diseño? ¿hasta que punto ha influido la idea de mantenimiento en sus decisiones de diseño?</p> <p>Pensando en el mantenimiento, ¿hay algo que hubieras hecho diferente a nivel de implementación/diseño?</p>
Impact and use (10)	<p>¿Que es el impacto que observáis ahora?</p> <p>(Additional trigger questions if needed, or not covered):</p> <p>¿Cuáles son vuestras impresiones del uso actual del patio por parte del alumnado: qué grupos, qué horas (solo durante el recreo o también para hacer clase), hay alguna diferencia entre niños y niñas ahora en comparación con antes? ¿Cambia el uso del lugar? ¿Alguna anécdota? ¿Funciona mejor el espacio en ciertos aspectos que antes? ¿De qué manera?)</p> <p>If these points below are not covered you can add also:</p> <p>¿Has observado cambios en el alumnado después del cambio del patio escolar? ¿En términos de interacción social, juego, desarrollo emocional, desarrollo cognitivo, capacidad de atención, cuidado de plantas/insectos (en caso que no se la mencionado)?</p>
Pedagogic implications (10)	<p>¿Crees que el “nuevo” patio es un espacio de enseñanza aprendizaje de contenidos y competencias curriculares?</p> <p>(Trigger questions: ¿Se utiliza para clases al aire libre? ¿Crees que podría (o debería) usarse más?)</p>

	<p>¿Cuáles son las oportunidades que ofrece y los obstáculos para que no se aproveche más?</p> <p>Pensáis que el profesorado necesitaría un poco mas de formación sobre enseñanza en el patio, o las zonas exteriores? Habrá interés si se ofrece ese topo de formaciones?</p>
<p>Accessibility and justice considerations (5 mins)</p>	<p>¿Esta abierto el patio en horarios fuera de los lectivos? Quien suele venir? Para que tipo de actividades?</p> <p>¿Piensas que las familias y grupos vulnerables a nivel económico y social tienen ahora más acceso a los beneficios del nuevo patio?</p>
<p>Concluding remarks (5mins)</p>	<p>¿Se te ocurre algo importante alrededor de la gobernanza de su patio escolar que no hemos abordado? ¿Alguna anécdota o recomendación que te gustaría compartir al final?</p> <p>¿O que hubieras hecho diferente?</p>